

Improving Accelerated MRI Reconstruction and Parametric Mapping with PENGUIN

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Introduction

Physics-based deep learning has been successfully applied to MRI image reconstruction from undersampled k-space, further pushing acceleration rates¹⁻³. In this work, we extended the Phase graph signal and Gradients QUantitative Inference MachiNe (PENGUIN) to perform T2 mapping directly from undersampled k-space to obtain higher quality reconstructions, and consequently more accurate quantitative maps, compared to networks tasked solely with reconstruction followed by a fitting step.

Methods

The PENGUIN⁴ (**Fig 1**) forward model is:

$$\mathbf{d} = \sum_{c=1}^C U \mathbf{F} S_c E(\mathbf{T}2),$$

with \mathbf{d} the measured k-space, C the number of coils, S the coil sensitivities, \mathbf{F} the Fourier Transform, U the undersampling mask, and E a pre-calculated dictionary of complex signal curves following the Extended Phase Graph framework (T2 values 0-2000 ms). The network was trained with BrainWeb⁵ simulated images, following a ME-SE acquisition sequence, TE=10:10:120 ms, flip angle=[180,160,...,160]°, and 2 simulated coil sensitivity maps along the anterior-posterior direction. Training data comprised 3000 2D slices from 10 distinct subjects; testing data, 5 slices each for another subject. Separate data was generated for acceleration factors 2, 4 and 8, with a radial k-space trajectory with golden angle increments between echoes and shots.

Results/Discussion

Fig 2 showcases the T2 maps obtained with Zero-Filled reconstruction followed by fitting and PENGUIN for a chosen test image. PENGUIN provides accurate images for all acceleration factors tested. For all the test set, the Zero-Filled method verified SSIM=[0.961±0.010, 0.930±0.015, 0.917±0.019] in the grey matter regions, SSIM=[0.979±0.12, 0.966±0.018, 0.949±0.020] in the white matter regions, and SSIM=[0.887±0.008, 0.817±0.013, 0.786±0.013] in the CSF, for acceleration factors 2, 4, and 8x respectively; comparatively, PENGUIN verified SSIM=[0.997±0.001, 0.992±0.003, 0.973±0.008] in the grey matter regions, SSIM=[0.998±0.001, 0.996±0.002, 0.982±0.012] in the white matter regions, and [SSIM=0.995±0.002, 0.994±0.002, 0.990±0.003] in the CSF, for the same acceleration factors.

Conclusion

PENGUIN is able to provide T2 maps directly from (up to 8-fold) undersampled k-space data. Pushing for higher acceleration factors is likely to require more complex networks hindering network optimization; it

remains to be seen whether a deeper network would be able to push acceleration factors while maintaining an advantage over equivalent methods lacking MR relaxometry modelling.

Novelty

PENGUIN directly estimates T2 maps from k-space in an end-to-end framework, whilst following an accurate signal model based on the EPG concept.

Impact

Including a relaxometry model into physics-informed reconstruction methods enables high quality quantitative mapping with accelerated acquisitions.

Disclosure

a) I or one of my co-authors have no financial interest or relationship to disclose regarding the subject matter of this presentation.

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Affix

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Fig 1. PENGUIN's architecture

PENGUIN architecture drawn for inference step j . At each optimization step, PENGUIN performs $J=6$ inference steps to obtain 6 estimates of the T2 maps \mathbf{p} . At each step j , PENGUIN receives the current estimate \mathbf{p}_j , a data consistency term, and two vectors of memory states, and outputs the incremental update to the estimate $\Delta\mathbf{p}_j$, and the updated memory states. The loss function was: $\Lambda^{total} = (1/J) \sum_{j=1}^J 10^{(j-1)/(J-1)} L_1(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p})$, where L_1 is the L1-norm loss.

Fig 2. T2 maps obtained with PENGUIN

a) Ground-truth and estimated T2 maps for acceleration factors 2, 4, and 8 obtained with Zero-Filled reconstruction and PENGUIN. **b)** Absolute difference between the estimated T2 maps and the ground-truth maps for acceleration factors 2, 4, and 8. PENGUIN provides T2 maps with the lowest error.